

VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF A PERSON AND THEIR FORMATION IN ADOLESCENT AGE

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Annotation: The will of a teenager is a certain set of mental properties that characterize the achieved level of conscious self-regulation of the individual. This set of properties develops throughout life. The article deals with the problems and questions of the formation of volitional qualities in adolescents.

Keywords: adolescence, volitional qualities, formation of volitional qualities, personality.

Introduction. Volitional qualities are one of the facets of personality. They are part of the character and, of course, are not inherited, they develop only in the process of upbringing and socialization [1]. Volitional qualities are relatively stable, independent of the specific situation mental formations, certifying the level of conscious self-regulation of behavior achieved by the individual, his power over himself [2, 3].

There are many positive and negative volitional qualities, so it is advisable to consider only the main ones. The most successful classification of volitional qualities is described in his research by D. Turdimurodov [4, 5, 6, 7]. Such volitional qualities as vigor, patience, endurance and courage are referred to as the main (primary) qualities of a personality, and the functional manifestations of these qualities are unidirectional regulatory actions of consciousness that take the form of volitional effort.

Thus, the will of a teenager is a certain set of mental properties that characterize the achieved level of conscious self-regulation of the individual. And this set of properties develops throughout life [8, 9, 10]. The volitional qualities of a person are relatively stable, independent of the situation, stable mental formations [11, 12].

Purposefulness is manifested in a person's curbing his behavior and striving for a certain life goal. This main goal determines more separate goals, the achievement of which becomes a means on the way to the main one. Independence is revealed in the ability of a person to adhere to his own principles, a single line of his own in actions, despite the pressure of society, the external situation [13, 14, 15]. Conscious curbing of one's own behavior to certain rules and norms is discipline [16, 17].

The structure of a person's will essentially depends on its content, that is, on the relationship between the particular-personal and the socially significant,

between the phenomenal and the essential. The volitional qualities of a person are among the most essential of his qualities, they have always played a leading role in the most magnificent events in the history of mankind: in heroic deeds and discoveries. The will arose in the labor activity of a person mastering the laws of nature, and thus having the opportunity to change it in accordance with his needs. K. Marx wrote: "In addition to the tension of those organs by which labor is performed, an expedient will is necessary during the entire time of labor".

In the structure of educational or labor activity, intentional actions form its higher level; they are characterized by a consciously set goal and the choice of means necessary to achieve this goal. "The more people move away from animals, the more their impact on nature takes on the character of deliberate, planned actions aimed at achieving certain, predetermined purpose", wrote F. Engels.

In a number of studies by some researchers, a number of characteristics of the features of the "style" of the activities of those adolescents in which there are shortcomings in the development of will have been identified [18]. These include the severity of the transition from a non-working state to the execution of purposeful actions, a long period of "buildup", an inability to monotony or detailed work, an inability to bring things to an end.

The activity of volitional self-affirmation begins in adolescence. For adolescents, the development of a strong will often acts as an end in itself [19, 20, 21]. This is a period of complex and contradictory formation of the volitional qualities of a person. Purposefulness in learning, independence, determination with which a teenager overcomes difficulties on the way to achieving the goal, indicate that he, according to the object of other people's freedom, gradually turns into the subject of his own will [22, 23]. But whether this process takes on positive forms or whether a perversion begins to arise depends on upbringing.

Adolescence is characterized by further intensive development of volitional qualities and, accordingly, the relative completeness of their formation. Volitional qualities become components and traits of a person's character. The behavior of high school students shows stability in the distribution of volitional efforts in accordance with the dominant interests. Volitional activity already meets social requirements [24].

But what volitional qualities and at what stage of completeness are included in the structure of a personality's character depends on many circumstances, including the process of adolescent self-affirmation, social choice and self-determination in adolescence, and self-education of each individual [25].

The peculiarity of volitional actions is that their goal, as a rule, is subordinated not to one, but to two or three or even more motives, different in content, strength and significance for the subject. Motives can be one direction or multidirectional. For example, an employee of an organization needs to prepare any package of documents. He is interested in his work, he intends to receive high wages, and wants his boss to especially highlight him. In this case, three different motives - learning, getting high and prestigious - have a universal focus, so that the struggle between them does not arise. Under their influence, the goal is formed - to do the job qualitatively.

Conclusions. In the psychological literature, there is an ambiguity in the views of specialists on the problem of the development of the will. There is still no consensus on the psychological structure of volitional actions; the basic terminological concepts, as well as the criteria for assessing readiness for volitional exertion, require clarification. At the same time, despite the variety of options for defining the will, we can confidently say that the will is the ability of a person to act in the direction of a consciously set goal, while overcoming external and internal obstacles. Will is a function of the human psyche, which consists in power over oneself, control over one's actions and conscious regulation of one's behavior in an effort to achieve a purpose.

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